

TEACHING PRIMARY VOLLEYBALL SKILLS AND ITS ESSENCE

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Abstract. *In this article, detailed information on the organization of training young volleyball players and the content, tasks, tools and training issues, as well as the wider popularization of the volleyball sport, is given.*

Keywords: *training, technical preparation, initial teaching, special exercises, the methods of teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

In addition to the development of physical education and mass sports, importance is being paid to the development of big sports in our country. Every year, international and world-class prestigious competitions are held in our republic, and the interest of young people in sports is increasing. Our athletes participate in Asian, World and Olympic competitions and achieve high results, glorifying the fame of our country. One of the ways to solve this problem is to redirect different types of targeted physical education programs to maximally meet the needs of each student, to fully take into account the level of physical development and training of students.

Unfortunately, although sports, especially volleyball, are widely developed, high results are not being achieved in international competitions. Volleyball is included in the curriculum of all educational institutions as a subject, sports clubs, children's and sports schools that operate outside of class and work on educational and training processes are being conducted.

The process of preliminary teaching of sports skills is the foundation of the long-term sports training system. The more thorough and high-quality the initial training is from the organizational, methodological, scientific and material-technical point of view, the shorter and easier the training of sports deputies will be. But this, of course, directly depends on the specialist's knowledge, professional skills and qualifications. Therefore, one of the most important and main sections of the training program for training specialists is the methodology (technology) of primary education.

It is known that the size and intensity of movement (load) is important for human health, its physical and functional formation. However, the volume and intensity of all types of movement, including physical and technical-tactical exercises performed in sports circles, should correspond to the functional capabilities of the participant or be slightly higher. Because, according to laws that have been proven in the science of biology, if the gross effect of the daily physical load performed at certain stages of ontogenetic development is always higher than the functional capabilities of the organism, then in this organism (organs, muscles, veins, cells, tissues, heart, lungs, spleen, liver, etc.) symptoms of stress or rapid exhaustion appear.

Such negative "traces" derail the normal functional activities of a person, especially a child, lower mood, disrupt sleep, ultimately reduce work ability and prevent him from fully recovering. If the predominance of such loads is chronically reversed in the child's activity, it can affect not only the normal growth of the organism, but it is possible that the predominance of these loads will lead to the appearance of local or global pathological complications in various functional "objects". On the contrary, if the volume and intensity of daily or gross training loads are lower

than the functional capacity, the formation of physical qualities slows down and work capacity does not increase. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the daily or gross loads, including the loads related to physical education classes and training sessions, depending on the age, gender, physical and functional capabilities of children in a "wave" principle. Therefore, the basis of pedagogical and medical supervision in the organization of children's sports training is an integral part of the process of raising a healthy, well-rounded generation.

Therefore, purposeful planning and management of the content of physical education and sports activities (physical education lessons, training sessions, sports competitions) is the responsibility of every specialist (teacher, coach, organizer, methodologist, etc.). It is necessary to assign a great responsibility to the leader to acquire knowledge related to physical culture, physical education, physical development, physical training and sports, and to acquire appropriate professional-pedagogical qualifications and skills.

One of the main factors for achieving an effective result during the competition is the technical preparation and technical skills of the volleyball player. Therefore, the first and main goal of the teaching process is to master the technique of the game perfectly.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Until now, a number of scientific researches devoted to the problems of physical education and sports theory and practice of higher educational institutions have been carried out, in which the issues of the differentiated methodology of using sports games in the sports improvement groups of higher educational institutions have been highlighted. In the scientific works of L.R. Ayrapetyans, M.A. Godik, 1991; Yu.D. Zheleznyak, 1994; M.C. Akhmatov, 2004; also V.A. Kobzev, 1996; N.A. Anashkina, 1998; A. Zelensky, 1998; V.P. Guba, 2000 and others, the theoretical and practical principles and methods of using a differentiated approach in organizing the physical education process of young students are described. Movement and game skills - passing the ball, receiving (defense), putting the ball into play, hitting, blocking are mastered and improved in certain stages, using certain methods and tools. This process is carried out on the basis of pedagogical, biopsychological and biomechanical laws.

RESULTS

The teaching process is a pedagogical process, which requires great skill and professional training from the trainer-teacher. But even so, the teaching of movement (game skill) technique depends on other important reasons. Including the child's activity, the number, quality, duration of training, auxiliary technical equipment, the conditions of the training place, the child's interest, wealth of movement, experience, etc. It should also be said that the period of mastering movement techniques depends on the child's family conditions, his social and economic opportunities, and his mental state.

The above-mentioned information and factors to be taken into account in the process of training should be included in planning documents based on a certain methodological procedure. In addition, it is necessary to identify the child's inner secret potential and existing factors with the help of selection programs and exercises. The obtained results should serve as a basis for the application of teaching methods, stages and technology.

The initial training process is carried out in several stages, and each of these stages includes its own methods and tools. General developmental exercises are used to improve the player's physical fitness and movement skills and skills necessary for the player.

All exercises should be combined in accordance with their direction form the main parts of special training, including general physical, special physical, technical, tactical and game training. Each type of preparation has its own leading factors, with the help of which the desired goal is achieved. At the same time, all types of preparations are inextricably linked. For example, if the student is not well prepared physically, he will not be able to perform well the technical exercise of hitting in attack. In this case, training the student from the physical side is more useful than repeating the hitting method many times. Initial training should be carried out step by step and based on the principle of training.

The first stage is to get acquainted with the studied movement technique. In this, the methods of telling, showing and explaining are used. In addition to showing, the coach uses visual aids such as film, visual film, scheme, field model, etc. The demonstration should be accompanied by explanations. The first attempts of the coach-teacher form in them the primary sense of movement.

The second stage is learning the technique in a simplified state. Success at this learning stage depends in many cases on the correct selection of approach exercises. According to their structure, they should be close to the movement technique being studied and students should be able to perform it. Actions with a complex structure, that is, an attack blow, are divided into its main components. At this stage, management methods are used: commanding, giving instructions, seeing and hearing, observing, technical means, etc. methods such as impact force, fall accuracy, light or sound are of particular importance.

The third stage is teaching technique in complicated conditions. The following are used in this: repetitive method, performance of movement in complex conditions, game and assessment method, joint method, circular exercises. Repetition is key at this stage. Repetition builds skill. Repetition in order to develop skills requires performing exercises in different conditions, changing the conditions of movement, and gradually increasing the complexity. Exercises are performed even when tired, joint and game styles are aimed at simultaneously polishing the technique and solving the issues of developing special physical qualities and improving technical and tactical training and playing skills.

The fourth stage is to strengthen the movement during the game. The method of interpretation of performed actions is used (pictures, tables, educational films, visual films), technical-tactical, special training tasks, game and competition methods are used during the game.

DISCUSSION

In preparation and educational games, it is envisaged to study each method (skill), improve and perfect it. The best way to improve skills is to compete.

The main means of training in volleyball, like other sports, is physical exercises. They are very different. Therefore, they are classified according to their role in solving the tasks at a certain stage of training. Such classification is based on the competitive activity of volleyball players. In this regard, exercises are divided into two large groups, these are the main or competition and auxiliary or training.

In many cases, the effectiveness of tools for training volleyball movements directly depends on the methods of their use. Styles are selected and applied depending on the assigned task, level of training of the participants, specific conditions.

Depending on the task, the same tool can be used in different ways. In addition, the sequence of tasks and types in each type of training has a certain logical connection.

Tasks of one type of training change in quality and create a foundation for the next type of training. For example, preparatory exercises represent the general structure of the technical method being studied. Convergence exercises serve as a bridge from special physical training to technical training. Technical exercises built on the basis of a certain level of complexity help to form tactical skills. On this basis, individual tactical actions will be studied later.

CONCLUSION

The main movement in volleyball consists of walking, running, side-stepping, back-stepping, step-stopping, jumping. In many cases, movements are interpreted as not difficult, and they are not given enough attention. This is a wrong idea. Because the choice of position and place for the player to perform various actions has a direct impact on the effect of the performed action. Therefore, it is necessary to pay great attention to teaching movements.

The correct organization of the initial training process of the coach serves as the basis for the effective formation of such important tasks as ensuring the integrity of the country's national teams and training qualified sports reserves.

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